

Numerical studies on the influence of natural convection under inclination on optimal aluminium proportions and fin spacings in a rectangular aluminium finned latent-heat thermal energy storage

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ABSTRACT

Phase change material (PCM) is applicable in various use cases, such as in a novel hybrid steam/latent heat storage system where containers filled with PCM are placed at the shell surface of a Ruths steam storage (RSS) for retrofitting. The considered approximately rectangular PCM cavity design includes aluminium fins, which is a common choice for heat transfer enhancement. Numerical studies were conducted with two separate numerical models to analyse melting and solidification of PCM in such cavity. Varying aluminium proportions, as well as varying fin spacings were simulated under different orientations of the PCM cavity and their impact on charging/discharging speed was analysed, providing a foundation for design optimization of the considered geometry. Guideline values for optimal aluminium ratio and optimal fin spacing could be obtained. Significant angular dependency on the thermophysical behaviour could be observed during melting, whereas the effect of natural convection during solidification was found to be negligible. The results of this work provide important insight to facilitate the design process of rectangular aluminium finned PCM cavities.

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

As a consequence of progressive decarbonisation efforts the energy-intensive industries are required to drastically increase energy efficiency. A large increase of thermal energy storage capacity in existing industrial plants and processes is therefore required in the future. Having the advantage of high energy density, Phase Change Material (PCM) is commonly used either in stand-alone storage systems, e.g., passive climatization modules in buildings, or to retrofit existing storage systems of other types. An overview of typical PCM and their application is given in Zalba et al. [1]. Dusek and Hofmann [2] presented a novel approach to increase the storage capacity of well-established Ruths steam storages (RSS) by attaching PCM containers to its outer shell. To ensure optimal use of latent heat thermal energy storages (LHTES) it is necessary to study the exact thermodynamic behaviour of the included PCM containers.

Different types of PCM encapsulations have been developed in the past, each tailored to the specific use case of interest (for an overview see, for example, Lin et al. [3], Zayed et al. [4], or Agyenim et al. [5]). PCM is typically placed in long thin heat pipes, cylindrical containers or rectangular containers, whereby the shell and tube system are the most intensely analysed LHTES type [5]. The typically low thermal conductivity of PCM prevents rapid heat transfer during charging (melting) and discharging (solidification) processes. Various techniques were developed to improve heat transfer rates in LHTES, e.g., using extended surfaces [6–8], high thermal conductivity porous matrices [9,10], heat pipes [11], nanoparticles [12] and carbon nanotubes [13], to mention a few. A very common approach for heat transfer enhancement is to equip the encapsulations with heat conductivity enhancement structures, such as flat-plate aluminium fins [14]. The application of such fins is particularly desirable due to the effectiveness in performance, ease in fabrication, and relatively low cost of construction [5]. In the hybrid storage approach presented by Dusek and Hofmann [2], PCM cavities are arranged around the cylindrical RSS where each cavity features aluminium fins orientated in the radial-axial plane of the RSS. Due to the

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Nomenclature			
Acronyms			
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics	ϕ	fin segment orientation
FDM	Finite Difference Method	ρ	density (kg m^{-3})
FEM	Finite Element Method	ρ_0	constant density of PCM (kg m^{-3})
LHTES	Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage	a	volumetric aluminium ratio
PCM	Phase Change Material	B	momentum source term coefficient (Pa s m^{-3})
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error	c	specific heat capacity ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
RSS	Ruths Steam Storage	f_l	liquid fraction
Index		h	specific enthalpy (J kg^{-1})
alu	aluminium	k	thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
conduction	conduction only reference case	L_x, L_y	length of PCM segment in x,y direction (m)
in	inner value	p	pressure (N m^{-2})
init	initial value	S_h	enthalpy source term
out	outer value	T	temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
ref	reference	t	time (s)
Parameters and variables		T_m	melting temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
α	heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$)	u, v	velocity components in x,y direction (m s^{-1})
β	volumetric thermal expansion coefficient (K^{-1})	w	aluminium fin spacing (m)
Δl_m	specific latent heat (J kg^{-1})	x, y	space coordinates (m)
Δt	time step (s)	\tilde{L}	characteristic length (m)
Δx_{PCM}	cavity PCM dimension in x direction (m)	τ	dimensionless time
Δy_{PCM}	cavity PCM dimension in y direction (m)	A	aspect ratio
\dot{Q}	heat flux (W)	A_{mush}	mushy zone constant ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)
ϵ	mushy region temperature range (K)	Fo	Fourier number
\hat{H}	enthalpy per unit volume (J m^{-3})	H	cavity height (m)
\mathbf{f}	force density ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-2}$)	Pr	Prandtl number
\mathbf{g}	gravitational acceleration vector (m s^{-2})	Ra	Rayleigh number
\mathbf{q}	specific heat flux (W m^{-2})	Ste	Stefan number
S_u	momentum source term	EF	convective enhancement factor
\mathbf{u}	velocity vector (m s^{-1})	Symbols	
μ	dynamic viscosity (N s m^{-2})	$\mathcal{D}, \partial \mathcal{D}$	spatial domain, boundary of spatial domain
		∇	Nabla operator: $\nabla = (\partial/\partial x, \partial/\partial y)$

typical dimensions of the hybrid storage, these fin segments are approximately rectangular, effectively making this a flat-plate rectangular PCM cavity design (for more details, see Section 2 and Fig. 1). In this work, numerical studies were conducted to analyse the melting and solidification of PCM in such encapsulation and thus providing essential

information to enable storage design optimization.

1.2. PCM simulation methods

Analytical solutions only exist for a limited number of phase change

Fig. 1. The location of the PCM cells attached to a RSS is illustrated, as proposed by Dusek and Hofmann [2]. Geometry and location of the considered PCM fin segment and adjacent fin segments and orientation relative to the gravitational vector are defined. Liquid PCM is depicted in yellow, solid PCM in blue. For details on PCM cell geometry, see Fig. 2. Note: This illustration is not true to scale.

problems, as for example for the one-dimensional Stefan-problem, see for example [15]. When treating problems in more than one dimension and considering heat transfer by conduction and convection, numerical methods have to be applied. Also, the Stefan problem is complicated by the fact that in general more than one moving phase boundary occur in PCM [16]. Liu et al. [17] and Dutil et al. [18] review options for mathematical modelling and simulation of PCM. The majority of these approaches uses the enthalpy method, as for example in Voller and Prakash [19] or the effective heat capacity method, as in Tenchev et al. [20], to account for phase change.

Although finite difference (FDM) and finite volume schemes are well established in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) applications, including the well-known software package *ANSYS Fluent*, Nedjar [21] states that especially finite element methods (FEM) are able to handle complex coupled thermomechanical problems with various and complex boundary conditions. Kasper [22] pursued an approach to couple an FEM implementation of the effective heat capacity method and an adaptation of the FDM code published by Seibold [23] to solve the 2D Navier–Stokes equations arising in convection modelling. This experimentally validated and highly adaptable model was applied for the parameter studies presented in this work, alongside with the CFD software *ANSYS Fluent*.

1.3. Previous studies

When designing PCM cavities, the thermodynamic behaviour has to be assessed in detail to enable optimal storage design regarding storage capacity and charging/discharging times. Natural convection can have a significant influence on this behaviour, additionally being dependent on the cavity orientation. Furthermore, the amount of heat transfer enhancing metal structures has to be optimized. Although the installation of fins can efficiently enhance PCM melting rate [24], it also restricts natural convection and reduces PCM volume and thus lowers the overall storage capacity [25]. Thus, fin dimensions as fin spacing and width should be appropriately selected to achieve better performance of the storage application [25–27]. These aspects were investigated to some extent and for specific PCM cavity geometries in previous studies, as the following review, primarily focussing on rectangular fin geometries, shows.

One important question is how natural convection in the liquid phase of the storage material influences the phase change problem. The relative influence of natural convection depends on both geometric parameters and PCM properties. Mostafavi Tehrani et al. [28] found a critical Rayleigh number of $8 \cdot 10^5$ below which natural convection is negligible in their respective shell-and-tube configuration. Dhaidan and Khodadadi [29] give an overview on melting with natural convection in different geometries. Numerous experimental and numerical analyses have been dedicated to melting in rectangular geometries, as for example by Bareiss and Beer [30], Benard et al. [31], Duan et al. [32] or Jany and Bejan [33]. However, Vogel et al. [34] state that the findings of this research are not directly applicable to large aspect ratio cavities and high temperature inorganic PCM, like $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$. In their respective work a flat plate LHTES, filled with the above-mentioned PCM, is analysed numerically, with a lab scale storage unit serving as experimental validation platform. Thereby, the influence of natural convection on the heat transfer rate was assessed by an introduced convective enhancement factor, providing a simple comparison of varying enclosure dimensions. Their results indicated that heat transfer enhancement due to natural convection increases with greater widths and smaller heights of storage material enclosures.

Many studies have already investigated the geometric and design parameters of heat transfer enhancing fins for PCM cavities [35]. Xie et al. [36,37] characterized the effects of metal structure, metal volume fraction and orientation and proposed optimized tree shape designs outperforming the flat plate designs. Xie et al. [38] suggested that their optimized tree shape structure is more superior in applications where

minimum conductive material is necessary and natural convection is significant. However, in a review on geometric and design parameters of fins employed for enhancing LHTES, Abdulateef et al. [35] state that the best enhancement is achieved using longitudinal finned configurations because of its easy design and fabrication. Lacroix and Benmadda [39] found in a numerical investigation that there is an optimum number of fins in a horizontal rectangular enclosure beyond which the melting rate decreases due to the weakening of convection currents. This was also found by Huang et al. [40] who reported that decreasing the fin spacing can impede the convective motion of liquid PCM between fins and therefore decreases the positive effect of fins. Biwole et al. [41] numerically studied the melting of paraffin in a vertical finned enclosure heated from one side. They varied number and thickness of the fins and found that using thinner but longer fins increases the heat transfer rate. Ye et al. [42] studied the effects of different cavity volume fractions of PCM on fluid flow and heat transfer behaviour. Bondareva and Sheremet [43] analysed the effect of fin height and width on convective melting intensity.

Regarding the orientation, i.e. inclination of PCM enclosures, Zhao et al. [44] theoretically and experimentally studied the contact melting of PCM in a rectangular cavity at different orientations and found that there is a unique optimal orientation to minimize melting time in the considered arrangement. Yang et al. [45] experimentally studied the effect of inclination and Yazici et al. [46] studied the combined effects of inclination angle and fin number on thermal performance of a PCM cavity, heated from their wide side. Their results revealed that the inclination angle and fin number plays a critical role on the formation of convective cells in the liquid PCM domain and consequently on the heat transfer and operating time. Sharifi et al. [47] studied the effect of orientation during outward melting from a concentrically heated rod placed inside a cylindrical enclosure. It was observed that even small tilting of the enclosure significantly affects the evolution of the melting front. In an investigation on melting of PCM in an unfinned rectangular enclosure with a specific fixed geometry for different Stefan numbers Kamkari et al. [48] found that when the orientation of the enclosure varies from 90° to 45° and 0° , the melting time reduces by 37% and 52%, respectively. In an experimental investigation, Kamkari and Groulx [49] analysed the effect of the cavity orientation on the melting rate for 1-fin and 3-fin rectangular enclosures and found small inclination angles to enhance melting in this specific enclosure geometry. This was confirmed in Karami and Kamkari [50] where this type of finned cavity was studied numerically under different inclination angles varied from 0° to 180° . Therein, the authors stress that limited attention has been given to the effect of orientation on the thermal behaviour of PCM in rectangular enclosures and that the only studies devoted to the effect of orientation on the melting process in finned PCM enclosures can be found in Kamkari and Groulx [49], Karami and Kamkari [50] and more recently in Groulx et al. [51]. Similar studies analysed the partly combined effects of fin spacing, thickness and angle on the optimum geometry for shell and tube LHTES configurations [52,53].

1.4. Main contributions

As can be seen from the above cited literature, numerous numerical and experimental studies on the effect of natural convection in PCM cavities have been published in recent years. Some of these considered different rectangular geometries, many analysed the design of heat enhancement fins and even studies of varying cavity orientation can be found, albeit very few. However, the findings of previous investigations are often difficult to exploit for different geometric characteristics. Many of the cited analyses cover rectangular enclosures heated/cooled from a wide side of the cavity, whereby this work focuses on heat transfer through one of the narrow sides of the cavity.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no experimental or numerical investigation has been conducted to study the combined effects of (i) aluminium proportions, (ii) fin spacing and (iii) cavity orientation on

charging/discharging speed of this type of rectangular PCM cavity arrangement. Hence, we consider the following as main contributions of this work:

- The effect of natural convection on charging (melting) and discharging (solidification) of a narrow rectangular finned PCM cavity was studied for different orientations. Significant angular dependency on the thermophysical behaviour was observed during charging, while the effect of natural convection during discharging was found to be negligible regardless of the orientation.
- The influence of the aluminium proportion of the finned cavity on the charging/discharging speed was evaluated, thus giving a measure for optimized cavity design.
- The influence of the aluminium fin spacings on the charging/discharging speed was studied, leading to quantitative statements about optimized fin configuration. The influence of natural convection is expressed by a convective enhancement factor for three different fin spacing configurations and varying cavity orientations.

This work presents how aluminium ratio and fin spacing of rectangular finned PCM cavity can be systematically optimized, hence guiding the design of applications as and similar to the concept proposed by Dusek and Hofmann [2]. The here presented study is essential for construction and the upcoming experimental investigations of this storage application.

1.5. Paper structure

This paper is organised as follows: In Section 2, the numerical modelling conducted for the presented parameter study is discussed and the applied *Fluent* and FEM/FDM model are explained in reasonable detail. The validation of these models is given in Section 3. The results of the conducted parameter studies are presented and discussed in Section 4. In Section 5, the main findings are highlighted and critically assessed and their practicality evaluated. Suggestions for further research are given.

2. Numerical modelling

The numerical models for the presented investigation are based on the following assumptions:

- Heat transfer is driven by conduction and natural convection.
- Material properties are constant in each phase but they can differ for the liquid and solid phases except for the density which is assumed to be constant and equal for both phases.
- Density is assumed to be constant except for the buoyancy term (Boussinesq approximation), and the only body force arises due to the gravitational acceleration in vertical direction. The flow is therefore considered incompressible, Newtonian and also laminar.
- Phase transition takes place in a small temperature region (“mushy region”) $T \in [T_m - \varepsilon, T_m + \varepsilon]$ around the melting temperature T_m and is only dependent on T (no hysteresis, no dynamics, no rate dependency).
- The depth of the rectangular enclosure in z-direction (as defined in Figs. 1 and 2) is assumed large enough for wall boundary layer effects to be negligible, hence the problem is reduced to two dimensions (no heat flow or convection in z-direction).
- Movement of the solid phase is neglected.
- Radiation and viscous dissipation is neglected.

The assumptions made herein are the same as those applied by Vogel et al. [34], who could successfully validate their model via experimental data. Since the same material of (KNO₃-NaNO₃) was used therein as in the present study and the geometry of the PCM cavity is considered very similar, we consider these assumptions justified. For general fin

Fig. 2. Definition of geometry of the considered PCM fin segment, including boundary conditions. Liquid PCM is depicted in yellow, solid PCM in blue. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

arrangements a three-dimensional cavity simulation might be required. However, the geometry of the regarded PCM cavities in this work of 120 mm, the fin segments exhibit an aperture angle of 5,6° for the widest considered fin spacing and of under 1,2° for more reasonable fin spacings under 20 mm. Hence, the diameter of the RSS is considered large against the width of the enclosure in y-direction, thus justifying a rectangular approximation of a fin segment. Fig. 2 illustrates the examined fin segment consisting of a rectangular aluminium enclosure filled with PCM. This segment is modelled in local coordinates (x, y) in the two-dimensional spatial domain \mathcal{D} and its boundary $\partial\mathcal{D}$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D} &= \{0 \leq x \leq L_x, 0 \leq y \leq L_y\} \\ \partial\mathcal{D} &= \partial\mathcal{D}_1 \cup \partial\mathcal{D}_2 \cup \partial\mathcal{D}_3 \cup \partial\mathcal{D}_4 \\ \partial\mathcal{D}_1 &= \{x = L_x, y \in \mathcal{D}\} \\ \partial\mathcal{D}_2 &= \{x \in \mathcal{D}, y = L_y\} \\ \partial\mathcal{D}_3 &= \{x = 0, y \in \mathcal{D}\} \\ \partial\mathcal{D}_4 &= \{x \in \mathcal{D}, y = 0\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

For the top and bottom walls ($\partial\mathcal{D}_2$ & $\partial\mathcal{D}_4$) adiabatic boundary conditions are applied based on the cavity's symmetry:

$$\mathbf{q}|_{\partial\mathcal{D}_2, \partial\mathcal{D}_4} = 0 \quad (2)$$

On the left and right sides of the domain ($\partial\mathcal{D}_1$ & $\partial\mathcal{D}_3$) type-3 boundary conditions, also known as Robin boundary conditions,

$$\mathbf{q}|_{\partial\mathcal{D}_3} = \alpha_{in} \cdot (T(x, y) - T_{in}) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{q}|_{\partial\mathcal{D}_1} = \alpha_{out} \cdot (T(x, y) - T_{out}) \quad (4)$$

are implemented, prescribing a heat flux dependent on the current boundary temperature $T(x, y)$, specified heat transfer coefficients α_{in} , α_{out} , and ambient temperatures T_{in} , T_{out} .

Regarding the planar velocity field $\mathbf{u} = [u, v]^T$ with its spatial components $u(x, y, t)$ and $v(x, y, t)$, no-slip boundary conditions are set for the domain boundaries,

$$\mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \quad (5)$$

as well as at in-domain phase boundaries. For details on the implementation, see [22].

In this work two different transient numerical models were utilized to study the melting and solidification behaviour of the PCM segment. The main model implements the corresponding equations for convection/conduction in MATLAB® [55] using an FEM/FDM approach. The auxiliary model simulates a PCM cell in *Fluent* and is used to provide validation of the main model. In the following subsections both model implementations are described.

2.1. ANSYS Fluent model

The model developed for the investigations on a PCM segment in *Fluent* uses the finite volume approach. It is a two-dimensional model with the expansion of one single cell in z-direction (symmetry boundary conditions). It is based on the Navier–Stokes equations for energy, momentum and mass conservation.

Fluent uses an enthalpy-porosity technique developed in [19,56] to describe the melting/solidification process. Thereby the melting front is not tracked explicitly, instead a liquid fraction $f_l \in [0, 1]$ is assigned to each cell. The liquid fraction is determined in each iteration via the enthalpy balance. With this approach melting/solidification at a certain temperature point (e.g., for pure substances or eutectic mixtures) as well as melting/solidification across a temperature range (“mushy region”) can be treated. The balance equations are applied for a mixture of both phases (liquid and solid) using the liquid fraction as compound (see [57]).

With the melting/solidification approach in *Fluent*, the PCM is assumed incompressible. Density gradients due to temperature distribution are considered to drive natural convection using the Boussinesq approximation.

2.1.1. Governing equations

The governing balance equations for energy, momentum and mass conservation are (for detailed descriptions see [34] or [57]):

$$\text{energy eq. : } \rho \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} h) = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + S_h \quad (6)$$

$$\text{momentum eq. : } \rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \rho (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = \mu \nabla \cdot (\nabla \mathbf{u}) - \nabla p + \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{S}_u \quad (7)$$

$$\text{continuity eq. : } \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (8)$$

In (6)–(8) ρ represents the constant density, μ the dynamic viscosity, p the pressure and T the temperature of a cell. In the enthalpy-porosity approach the specific enthalpy h is the sum of the sensible enthalpy h_s and the latent heat Δl_m according to the liquid fraction f_l (9). In this work, ∇ and Δ are the Nabla and Laplace operators respectively. The enthalpy source term S_h (10) is introduced to discretize the energy equation as a single phase for a two-phase problem.

$$\text{enthalpy of a cell : } h = h_s + f_l \Delta l_m \quad (9)$$

$$\text{enthalpy source term : } S_h = \rho \frac{\partial (f_l \Delta l_m)}{\partial t} + \rho \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} f_l \Delta l_m) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{momentum source term : } \mathbf{S}_u = -B \mathbf{u} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{buoyancy term : } \mathbf{b} = \rho \beta (T - T_{\text{ref}}) \mathbf{g} \quad (12)$$

The buoyancy term \mathbf{b} from (7) is defined with the Boussinesq approximation, a reference temperature T_{ref} , the gravity vector \mathbf{g} and a volumetric thermal expansion coefficient β in (12). The momentum source term \mathbf{S}_u in (11) is a damping term for (8). This term must be zero for a

cell in liquid state but becomes very large for a cell in solid state to ensure velocities near zero. The term

$$B = A_{\text{mush}} \frac{(1 - f_l)^2}{f_l^3 + 10^{-3}} \quad (13)$$

in (11) is a function of the liquid fraction and a mushy zone constant A_{mush} , as defined in [34,58]. This is an adaption of the Carman-Koseny equation [59]. A large mushy zone constant results in a strong damping of convection in the transition area between liquid and solid (“mushy region”). Shmueli et al. [60] investigated the influence of the value A_{mush} for a material with a mushy region and find a great variation of results with different values of A_{mush} . More recent investigations can be found in Fadl and Eames [61], Kumar and Krishna [62] or Arena et al. [63]. Although overall large influence of the parameter on the results have been obtained, Vogel et al. [34] state that with a smaller mushy region, the mushy zone constant becomes less important.

2.1.2. Discretization

The pressure-based solver SIMPLE developed by Patankar [64] is selected for pressure-velocity coupling in the balance equations. The second-order differencing scheme was used for solving the momentum and energy equations, whereas the interpolation of pressure values at the cell faces is done with the PRESTO! scheme. The temporal derivatives are discretized with a second-order implicit transient formulation. The convergence criterion for continuity, velocity components in x- and y-directions, and energy are 10^{-4} , 10^{-4} and 10^{-8} respectively. The underrelaxation factors for the velocity components, pressure correction, thermal energy and liquid fraction were 0.4, 0.8, 1 and 0.4, respectively. It has been observed that several iterations are required to obtain convergent results for an underrelaxation factor of the liquid fraction this low. Therefore the minimum number of iterations is set to 20.

2.2. FEM/FDM model

The developed FEM/FDM model used for the simulation studies in this work was developed by Kasper [22] and is outlined in the following.

2.2.1. Governing equations

The governing equations within the framework of assumptions are the energy Eq. (14), continuity Eq. (15) and Navier–Stokes Eq. (16), which are in this work implemented as follows:

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k \nabla \cdot (\nabla T) - \rho c \nabla \cdot (T \cdot \mathbf{u}) \quad (14)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \right) - \mu \nabla \cdot (\nabla \mathbf{u}) + \nabla p = \mathbf{f} + \mathbf{S}_u \quad (16)$$

Therein, the temperature field $T(x, y, t)$ is treated as dependent variable in the energy Eq. (14) and the velocity field \mathbf{u} is treated as dependent variable in the Navier–Stokes Eq. (16), see [65]. The symbols denote the parameters density ρ , apparent heat capacity

$$c = \begin{cases} c_{\text{solid}} & \text{if: } T_m - \varepsilon > T, \\ \frac{\Delta l_m + c_{\text{solid}} \cdot (T_m + \varepsilon - T) + c_{\text{liquid}} \cdot (T - (T_m + \varepsilon))}{2\varepsilon} & \text{if: } T_m - \varepsilon < T < T_m + \varepsilon, \\ c_{\text{liquid}} & \text{if: } T > T_m + \varepsilon, \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

heat conductivity k and dynamic viscosity μ . The force density \mathbf{f} formulates the buoyancy force

$$\mathbf{f} = \rho \mathbf{g} = \rho_0 \mathbf{g} (1 - \beta (T - T_{\text{ref}})), \quad (18)$$

which is calculated as given in Huang et al. [66] by the volumetric thermal expansion coefficient β , the constant density ρ_0 , a reference temperature T_{ref} and the gravitational standard acceleration vector \mathbf{g} . The source term S_u as defined in (11) is added to modulate the additional viscous force with respect to the liquid fraction f_l .

2.2.2. Discretization

The FEM/FDM discretization of the governing Eqs. (14)–(16) is outlined in the following. For more details, refer to Kasper [22] or Pernsteiner et al. [67].

The energy Eq. (14) is discretised in space using a standard Galerkin FEM. Four-noded bilinear rectangular elements are used to obtain a finite element representation of the temperature field $T(x,y,t)$. Using this finite element representation and applying Galerkin's method of weighted residuals (see, for example, [68]) results in a system of ordinary differential equations. To compute the coefficient matrices, the surface and volume integrals are split into the finite element domains and are then numerically solved applying two-point Gauss–Legendre quadrature and three-point Gauss–Lobatto quadrature for the convection terms. The ordinary differential equation system is solved implicitly for the temperature field at the next time step by applying the backwards Euler method.

The velocity field components $u(x,y,t)$ and $v(x,y,t)$ and the set of incompressible 2D Navier–Stokes Eq. (16) are treated separately from the heat transfer part of the model by applying a finite difference discretization based on a MATLAB® code available on the course homepage (<http://math.mit.edu/~gs/cse/>) of “Computational Science and Engineering” at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. This open source code, created and documented by Seibold [23] was implemented and extended to meet specific tasks in the work [22]. The main numerical concept used therein is the fractional step method [69], which is applied to split the Navier–Stokes system into equations that are significantly simpler to work with. The solution update for the velocity is then found by executing a three-step approach, (1) an explicit time step for the nonlinear convective acceleration terms, (2) an implicit time step for linear viscosity terms and (3) a pressure correction step.

The spatial discretization via the FDM is conducted using a staggered grid based on the finite element mesh, where the pressure p is defined in the element centres, u values are defined in the middle of the vertical element edges and the values of v are defined in the middle of the horizontal element edges (see [22,23]).

3. Validation

The numerical models utilized herein were validated by experimental data (see Section 3.1). Furthermore, a cross validation of the FEM/FDM model and the *Fluent* model is given based on a number of reference cases which are part of the parameter study conducted in the scope of this work (see Section 3.2). The conducted independence study of grid size and time step for the presented parameter study is discussed in Section 3.3. Details on the grid size and time step independence for the experimental validation case can be found in Kasper [22] for the FEM/FD model.

Regarding the independence study for the *Fluent* model, we found a difference of 2.6% in the liquid fraction value after 20 min between simulations with $\Delta x = \Delta y = 0.5$ mm and $\Delta x = \Delta y = 1.0$ mm. Furthermore we found a difference in the liquid fraction value of 0.03% between simulations with $\Delta t = 0.1$ s and $\Delta t = 0.01$ s. We consider the grid and time step as converged with $\Delta x = \Delta y = 1.0$ mm and $\Delta t = 0.1$ s and used these parameters for comparison with the experimental reference case.

3.1. Experimental validation

The conduction/convection models used in the here presented study

were validated with the benchmark experiment of Gau and Viskanta [70], who investigated the melting and solidification behaviour of gallium in a rectangular enclosure. Furthermore, comparison with the numerical results of Brent et al. [71], Kumar et al. [72] is given.

The mushy zone constant A_{mush} for this problem was varied between 10^5 and 10^9 kg m⁻³s⁻¹. The best agreement with the experimental data was obtained for the value $A_{mush} = 10^8$ kg m⁻³s⁻¹ and is given below.

Very good agreement of the simulated melted volume fraction compared to the experimental data was found for the FEM/FDM model, with a root mean squared error of below 3% (for details, see [22]). The quantitative agreement between the simulations in this work and the benchmark experimental and numerical results is reasonable for all compared times, capturing regions of different melting regimes. A comparison of the simulated and reference melting front at three different times is given in Fig. 3. A comparison of the liquid fraction is given in Fig. 4, together with the root mean square error (RMSE) calculated from the respective given melting front data. Minor quantitative deviations can be obtained therein. The melting progresses slightly slower in the FEM/FDM simulation and fits reasonably well to the experimental data. In the *Fluent* simulation, melting progresses faster, similar to the reference case by Kumar et al. [72]. It should be noted, that discrepancies between the FEM/FDM and *Fluent* model were found to be smaller for the parameter studies of KNO₃-NaNO₃, see Section 3.2.

Remaining deviations to the experimental data of Gau and Viskanta [70] generally arise from inconsistencies between the assumptions of selected mathematical model and the exact experimental procedure [73]. Some controversy about the flow structure for this investigation and therefore the case's adequacy as validation benchmark still remains. Some researchers suggest that the correct solution should feature multiple convective cells [73], while three-dimensional simulations showed the absence of multiple convective cells [74]. To further verify the accuracy of the present investigation, a numerical cross validation of the two developed models was conducted.

3.2. Numerical cross validation

In total 24 reference cases of the following parameter studies were simulated using both the FEM/FDM and *Fluent* models. These cases included melting and solidification, fin spacings w of 12.5 mm, 25.0 mm, 50.0 mm, aluminium volumetric ratios a of 4%, 8% and 16% and segment orientations ϕ of 0°, 45°, 90°, 135°, 180°, as well as cases considering only conduction. The maximum obtained RMSE of the simulated enthalpy change values was 15.6%. The RMSE over all 24

Fig. 3. Melting front results of the developed numerical models compared to experimental and numerical reference results at three different times of the melting progress.

Fig. 4. Liquid fraction results of the developed numerical models compared to experimental and numerical reference results.

reference values and all logged time steps for the relative deviation of the enthalpy change values was 3.8%. We consider these as small discrepancies between the two models for the regarded simulation cases, therefore providing another verification of the conducted simulation studies in this work.

3.3. Grid size and time step independence study

The accuracy implications of the element grid and time step sizes were carefully tested to keep the computational effort in reasonable limits.

The mushy zone constant A_{mush} for this problem is chosen to be 10^6 which is in the recommended range by ANSYS® Fluent, Release 16.0 [57]. This value lies in accordance with [34], and their experimental validation while using (KNO₃-NaNO₃).

3.3.1. ANSYS Fluent model

The geometry and mesh creation was carried out with ANSYS Workbench [75]. To ensure mesh and time step independency, convergence studies were performed. The rectangular and structured mesh consists of 240×50 elements in x- and y-direction, respectively. To achieve a volumetric mesh, one element and symmetry boundary conditions are used in z-direction. A uniform time step of $\Delta t = 0.05$ s was applied for all simulated reference cases during the numerical cross validation.

Fig. 5. Grid size sensitivity for simulation case with $w = 12.5$ mm, $\alpha = 8\%$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$. Carried out with a time step size $\Delta t = 0.05$.

3.3.2. FEM/FDM model

For the finite element simulations, uniformly distributed grids of 12000 elements presented adequate resolution. The grid size sensitivity is illustrated for a reference simulation case in Fig. 5. Further refinement showed non-significant impact on the simulation results within the scope of this investigation, which holds true for all simulated geometries. Furthermore, the effect of time step size was investigated and a time step size of $\Delta t = 0.05$ s was selected for the simulation studies. Fig. 6 shows good convergence of the solution for this value. The selected grid and time step proved accurate and sufficient to meet the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition [76]

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t &\leq \Delta x / |u|, \\ \Delta t &\leq \Delta y / |v|, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\Delta x, \Delta y$ are the mesh resolutions and $|u|, |v|$ the magnitudes of the velocity in x- and y-direction. Fig. 7 illustrates the maximum CFL numbers in the liquid domain in x- and y-direction for all here investigated cases over the whole duration of the simulation.

4. Results and discussion

In this Section, the results of the parameter study regarding charging/discharging performance of the considered PCM storage design are illustrated by a number of representative results and discussed. While the considered materials' thermophysical properties remained unchanged (see Section 4.1.2), three geometrical aspects were varied, which is explained in Section 4.1.1.

4.1. Parameter study remarks

Since this work presents a foundation to thermal energy storage design optimization for industrial applications, the characteristic measure investigated herein is the total stored thermal energy, i.e. total enthalpy [54]. For further comprehension of the results, illustrations of latent enthalpy and convective enhancement are presented.

It should be noted that the obtained results highly depend on all three varied geometrical aspects. As it is not possible to study the influence of all three at the same time, the herein given results are presented in a way where at least one aspect is always constant. However, the extent of the presented results allow to fully assess the design characteristics in the considered parameter range.

Small oscillations of the calculated heat flux can be obtained, which are attributed to the nature of the finite element discretization and shape functions in combination with the apparent heat capacity method, which are known for supporting spurious oscillations [77]. However, careful comparisons of numerical errors over discretization fineness as

Fig. 6. Time step sensitivity for simulation case with $w = 12.5$ mm, $\alpha = 8\%$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$. Carried out with a grid size of 12000 elements.

Fig. 7. Scatter plot of the maximum CFL numbers in the liquid domain for all investigated cases over the whole simulation duration.

mentioned above have been carried out to control these numerical errors. Similar oscillations can be found in other numerical investigations, as for example [41], not affecting the qualitative results.

4.1.1. Geometry

As described in Section 2, the PCM storage design of interest is that of PCM filled aluminium encapsulations including plane parallel aluminium fins. A fin segment of such cavity is illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2. The conducted parameter study presented in this work focused on three main geometrical aspects:

- (i) the aluminium fin spacing $w = L_y$,
- (ii) the aluminium-to-PCM ratio $a = 2\Delta y_{\text{alu}}/L_y$ in vol% (neglecting the aluminium share introduced by Δx_{alu}),
- (iii) the fin segment orientation ϕ , as defined in Fig. 1.

In all studies, the material properties as well as the wall thickness of the heated wall $\Delta x_{\text{alu}} = 2$ mm were held constant in this study. Also, the segment length $L_x = 120$ mm is kept constant, which is done because in previous research, this value was found optimal for the considered PCM arrangement and for a specific industrial use case with charging/discharging cycle times of about 3 h. The underlying design optimization was published in Hofmann et al. [54].

4.1.2. Material properties

The considered PCM is an eutectic mixture of potassium nitrate and sodium nitrate $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$ which is commonly used for high-temperature phase change thermal storage systems [78]. Its properties were obtained from Vogel et al. [34] and are given in Table 1, including values for the liquid state (L) and solid state (S), alongside the utilized property data of the simulated aluminium encapsulation. Variable properties of specific heat capacity c and heat conductivity k are approximated in this study by different, but constant values for the liquid and solid state. A similar approach for this material was pursued

Table 1
Material properties of the considered LHTES used in this study. Source: Vogel et al. [34].

Property	PCM ($\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$)	Aluminium
density $\frac{\rho}{\text{kg m}^{-3}}$	2050	2700
spec. heat capacity $\frac{c}{\text{J}(\text{kg K})^{-1}}$	1350 (S) 1492 (L)	910
heat conductivity $\frac{k}{\text{W}(\text{mK})^{-1}}$	0.457 (S) 0.435 (L)	237
melting temperature $\frac{T_m}{^\circ\text{C}}$	220 (± 0.1)	–
spec. latent heat $\frac{\Delta l_m}{\text{kJ}(\text{kg})^{-1}}$	108	–
thermal expansion coefficient $\frac{\beta}{(\text{K})^{-1}}$	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–
dynamic viscosity $\frac{\mu}{\text{Ns}(\text{m})^{-2}}$	$5.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–

by Vogel et al. [79], who set the properties for the charging process to the values of the solid state and for the discharging process to the value of the liquid state. The authors stated that this simplifies the model and results in better convergence of the governing equations and resulting deviations are considered to be rather small.

4.1.3. Initial and boundary conditions

The melting temperature of the simulated PCM was set to $T_m = 220$ °C, with a mushy region of $\pm \varepsilon = \pm 0.1$ °C. For charging simulations, the whole storage cell was initialized at a temperature of $T_{\text{init}} = 219$ °C, and a left-hand side heating temperature of $T_{\text{in}} = 230$ °C was prescribed, with a fixed heat transfer coefficient of $\alpha_{\text{in}} = 700$ W/mK. This value of α_{in} corresponds to the heat transfer from liquid water to metal [80,81]. For discharging simulations, the initialization temperature was set to $T_{\text{init}} = 221$ °C and a left-hand side temperature of $T_{\text{in}} = 200$ °C was applied. The insulation of the PCM cell was considered perfect in the scope of transient charging/discharging simulations, hence the right-hand side was considered adiabatic corresponding to a heat transfer coefficient of $\alpha_{\text{in}} = 0$ W/mK. The duration of the simulation was in most cases 3 h, as argued above. Selected simulation cases were defined to cover a longer charging duration, to observe full liquefaction of the PCM.

4.2. Effects of angular dependency

To illustrate the angular dependency of convection effects in the PCM cavity, the progression of enthalpy per unit volume over time during charging and discharging is given in Fig. 8 for fixed cavity parameters $w = 25.0$ mm and $a = 8\%$. Five different cavity orientations were simulated and compared to the case considering only heat conduction. Fig. 8a shows significant influence for the upwards-oriented cavities (0° , 45°), whereas convection effects are small for the orientation angles 135° and 180° for this geometry. It should be noted however, that these findings differ from cases with larger fin spacings, as discussed in Section 4.4, where convection effects are very significant also for downwards orientated cavities. Furthermore, the influence of convection effects also depends on the aluminium ratio a , because the melting shape and therefore convective domains in the PCM cavity change significantly with the altered distribution of heat into the PCM.

Convective effects during solidification were found negligible, which is illustrated by Fig. 8b. This result was also found for other values of fin spacing and aluminium besides for the fixed cavity parameters $w = 25.0$ mm and $a = 8\%$ and therefore proved independent of fin spacing and aluminium. For this reason, we focused on the charging scenario in the remainder of this parameter study. It should be noted, however, that the obtained result of negligible convective effects during solidification regardless of orientation, fin spacing, or aluminium ratio is restricted to the considered cavity geometry and especially to the chosen discharging scenario. For example, results might differ for discharging scenarios starting at higher temperatures, where convection is expected to be effective in the initial cooling phase. The observed insensitivity of convective heat transfer during discharging is attributed to the effect that the PCM, with its low thermal conductivity, acts as an insulator once solidification at the aluminium fins sets in. Thereby, the temperature gradient inside the - now well insulated - liquid sub-domain is small and convection is negligible. The fact that natural convection is negligible during the discharge of LHTES was already reported by, for example, [82,83]. The only reason natural convection can affect the solidification process is very high sensible heating of the liquid or heating from the boundary. However, these effects seem negligible in the here considered PCM cavity design.

4.3. Effects of aluminium ratio

The ratio of aluminium to PCM in this cavity design has strong impact on the charging/discharging performance. Higher aluminium

Fig. 8. Progression of enthalpy per volume over time during charging (a) and discharging (b), referenced to the starting point, for fixed fin spacing $w = 25.0$ mm, aluminium ratio $a = 8\%$ and different segment orientations ϕ compared to conduction only case.

shares result in better heat conductivity and therefore faster cavity charging/discharging, while at the same time the sum of specific heat capacity and specific latent heat per unit volume is reduced. Therefore, the choice of aluminium ratio faces a trade-off between storage capacity and charging/discharging speed. The results discussed in this work give indicators to support such decisions. The relation between the total storage capacity in the considered charging scenario of the cavity and its aluminium ratio is given in Fig. 9.

The effect of three exemplary aluminium ratios $a = 4\%$, $a = 8\%$ and $a = 16\%$ on charging speed (specific heat flux/ Wm^{-2}) is illustrated for three different fin spacings and for cavity orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ and the case considering only conduction in Fig. 10. For the small fin spacing of $w = 12.5$ mm, we obtain only small heat flux enhancement due to convection, whereas it is significantly higher for fin spacings $w = 25.0$ mm and $w = 50.0$ mm. This effect will be discussed in detail in Section 4.4. It should also be noted that the reason of the sudden drop in heat flux towards the end of the charging process for aluminium ratios $a = 8\%$ and $a = 16\%$ is caused by the cavity reaching full liquefaction and therefore its maximum capacity. This becomes apparent by examining Fig. 11, where the change of latent heat per volume over time for the same particular charging cases is given.

Upon close examination of Fig. 10b, which shows charging speeds of cavities with fin spacing $w = 25.0$ mm, a slight but sharp increase in heat

flux can be obtained at around 80 min. The reason for this is an intensification of convection in the cavity as soon as the liquid PCM area reaches a critical size. After this point, the heat flux remains nearly constant until it drops again due to the previously mentioned completion of charging. The small time gap between the onset of this heat flux increase of the different aluminium ratio cases is assumed to have two reasons. Firstly, the PCM area is naturally slightly narrower for cavities with wider fins resulting of higher aluminium ratios. It therefore takes more time until the liquid PCM area reaches a critical size. Secondly, due to higher aluminium ratios also a higher amount of heat is transferred through the fins and effectively further into the cavity domain, which in turn leads to a different melting behaviour. As can be interpreted from temperature distributions of these cases, the liquid PCM area consists of rather narrow parts, where convection is limited. In contrast, cases with lower aluminium ratio develop a wide liquid PCM area near the heated wall, since heat transfer through the fins to the opposite side of the heated wall is comparatively smaller.

4.3.1. Optimal aluminium ratio

To obtain information about the optimal ratio of aluminium for the considered cavity geometry, aluminium ratios between 2% and 40% in increments of 2% were simulated for fixed fin spacing $w = 25.0$ mm and segment orientations $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ as well as the conduction only case. Fig. 12 illustrates the results of this investigation by means of the time needed to reach particular charging levels, expressed by the enthalpy change per unit volume referenced to the starting value. From these charging levels, the relative charging level can be obtained from the relation in Fig. 9, which also shows that the charging level of $2.0 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$ can not be reached in case of aluminium ratios above 22%, same as $1.7 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$ for aluminium ratios above 36%.

Looking at the lower charging levels of $0.8 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$ and $1.3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$ in Fig. 12, no significant difference between convection cases and conduction only case exists, except for very small aluminium ratios. For higher charging levels of $1.7 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$ and $2.0 \cdot 10^8 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$ though, this difference is quite pronounced. These high charging levels are reached faster by segment orientations $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 45^\circ$ compared to $\phi = 90^\circ$ and considerably faster compared to the conduction only case. This is especially distinctive for small aluminium ratios, where in some cases the chosen charging levels could not be reached within the 3 h charging scenario.

Looking at the two lower charging levels, it can be seen that aluminium ratios above 15 to 20% just lead to marginal reductions of the charging time. The same conclusion can be drawn at the two higher charging levels, where the time needed to reach the charging level even increases with the upper values of the illustrated aluminium ratios. This

Fig. 9. Dependency of total storage capacity (enthalpy per unit volume) and its sensible and latent part on aluminium ratio for the considered cavity design and charging scenario.

Fig. 10. Effect of different aluminium ratios on charging speed (specific heat flux) for segment fin spacings (a) $w = 12.5$ mm, (b) $w = 25.0$ mm, (c) $w = 50.0$ mm and segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

Fig. 11. Effect of different aluminium ratios on progression of latent enthalpy per volume over time during charging, referenced to the starting point, for segment fin spacings (a) $w = 12.5$ mm, (b) $w = 25.0$ mm, (c) $w = 50.0$ mm and segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

however is of course caused by the limited storage capacity and the fact that the heat flux diminishes towards the end of charging due to the absence of high temperature gradients.

All in all, for the investigated cases and charging scenario, an aluminium ratio of about 10 to 15% appears to be the optimal choice, presenting an efficient trade-off between fast charging time and overall storage capacity.

4.4. Effects of aluminium fin spacing

Although the aluminium fin spacing should be as small as possible when neglecting the effect of natural convection, it has been shown that decreasing the fin spacing can impede the convective motion of the

liquid PCM and therefore decrease their positive effects (see, for example [39,40]). The effect of three exemplary fin spacings $w = 12.5$ mm, $w = 25.0$ mm and $w = 50.0$ mm on charging speed (specific heat flux [Wm^{-2}]) is illustrated in Fig. 13 for three different aluminium ratios $a = 4\%$, $a = 8\%$ and $a = 16\%$ and for segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ and the case considering only conduction. The change of latent heat per volume over time for these charging cases is given in Fig. 14, similar to Fig. 11 in Section 4.3. Figs. 13 and 14 show that for the fin spacing $w = 12.5$ mm convection effects lead to only small enhancement in specific heat flux, with the exception of small aluminium ratio $a = 4\%$. This becomes apparent especially in the case of high aluminium ratio $a = 16\%$. Furthermore, while smaller fin spacings lead to overall higher heat flux and faster charging times in the conduction only cases and especially for

Fig. 12. Effect of different aluminium ratios on time to reach charging level (enthalpy per volume) for fixed fin spacing $w = 25.0$ mm and different segment orientations $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

Fig. 13. Effect of different fin spacings on charging speed (specific heat flux) for aluminium ratios (a) $a = 4\%$, (b) $a = 8\%$, (c) $a = 16\%$ and segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

high aluminium ratio, the same can not be said for the convection case with orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$. While the small fin spacings produce high heat fluxes and faster charging times compared to the cases with fin spacings of $w = 25.0$ mm and $w = 50.0$ mm in the case of high aluminium ratio $a = 16\%$, for the lower aluminium ratios $a = 4\%$ and $a = 8\%$ the charging times are almost identical. The cases with fin spacings $w = 25.0$ mm even surpass the charging speed of the small fin spacings $w = 12.5$ mm, as shown in Fig. 14a and b.

It can be concluded that the heat transfer by natural convection is substantial especially in case of large fin spacings and small aluminium ratios. To quantify this impact of natural convection on the heat transfer, the convective enhancement factor

$$EF(\hat{H}) = \frac{\dot{Q}(\hat{H})}{\dot{Q}_{\text{conduction}}(\hat{H})} \quad (20)$$

is calculated, as introduced by Vogel et al. [34]. It is defined as the ratio of the actual heat flux considering natural convection to a hypothetical heat flux by heat conduction only. Since time scale and phase front progression are different in each case, both heat flux values are evaluated at equal enthalpy per volume \hat{H} , which approximates to the liquid phase fraction f_l . The convective enhancement factors for fixed aluminium ratio $a = 8\%$ for three particular fin spacings and segment orientations ranging from 0° to 180° are illustrated in Fig. 15. Enhancement factors of up to $EF = 2$ arise in case of fin spacing $w = 12.5$

Fig. 14. Effect of different fin spacings on progression of latent enthalpy per volume over time during charging, referenced to the starting point, for aluminium ratios (a) $a = 4\%$, (b) $a = 8\%$, (c) $a = 16\%$ and segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

Fig. 15. Convective enhancement factor for aluminium ratio $a = 8\%$ and fin spacings (a) $w = 12.5$ mm, (b) $w = 25.0$ mm, (c) $w = 50.0$ mm for different segment orientations ϕ .

mm, while for the wider fin spacings $w = 25.0$ mm and $w = 50.0$ mm enhancement factors of up to $EF = 2.8$ and $EF = 3.6$ arise, respectively. Looking at Fig. 15a and b, low convective enhancement factors and therefore negligible influence of natural convection on heat transfer for downwards orientated segments (orientation $\phi = 105^\circ, 120^\circ, 135^\circ, 180^\circ$) can be obtained. Fig. 15c however shows convective enhancement factors of up to $EF = 2$ for these downwards orientated segments. In case of wide fin spacings, as in the case $w = 50.0$ mm, heat is thus transferred downwards through the aluminium fins and natural convection in this case transfers heat back up the segment, hence increasing the heat distribution.

Regarding the convective enhancement in upwards orientated segments, almost the same behaviour can be observed for the orientations $\phi = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$ in the corresponding fin spacing cases. An

exception to this is the segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ for the fin spacing $w = 12.5$ mm, where the convective enhancement factor decreases after the initial charging phase and after that shows high variability and is considerably lower than that of segment orientations $\phi = 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$. This interesting effect can be explained by observing the velocity distribution during the charging of this segment. The liquid area in the PCM part of the segment has to reach a particular size so that convection effects become crucial. In case of the segment with small fin spacing $w = 12.5$ mm and orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$, two separate convection vortices form due to symmetry, both being too small to strongly affect the heat transfer enhancement. A slight tilt of the segment however breaks this symmetry, leading to a single convection vortex. This therefore covers a larger liquid PCM area resulting in stronger convection and heat transfer enhancement.

4.4.1. Optimal fin spacing

To investigate the optimal fin spacing for this type of PCM cavity geometry, an aluminium ratio of 8% was selected and segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ as well as the conduction only case were compared for different fin spacings. In a preliminary parameter study, fin spacings between 5 mm and 100 mm in increments of 6.25 mm were simulated. The results are illustrated in Fig. 16 similarly to Fig. 12 in Section 4.3. In this case the charging levels are expressed by % of the total storable enthalpy per volume of the fin segment, since this value is equal for all compared cases with all of them having the same aluminium ratio. As expected, in the conduction only case the charging time increases with increasing fin spacing, which is also true for the time to reach the charging level 30% when considering convection, since up to this point heat transfer is still dominated by conduction. For the cases considering convection though, an optimal fin spacing value can be obtained for each case. For segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ a fin spacing of $w = 18.75$ mm leads to the fastest time to reach the charging levels 70% and 90%, while the charging level of 50% is reached slightly faster with a fin spacing of $w = 12.5$ mm. For segment orientations $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ fin spacings of $w = 12.5$ mm lead to the fastest charging times.

Based on the results of the preliminary study to find an optimal fin spacing, a second parameter study with refined resolution was conducted to eliminate errors and achieve improved results. Fig. 17 shows the results of this investigation, where additionally fin spacings between 5 mm and 30 mm in increments of 1.25 mm were simulated. For segment orientation $\phi = 45^\circ$ fin spacings between $w = 10$ mm and $w = 15$ mm lead to the fastest charging times. The findings of fin spacing optimum between $w = 15.0$ mm and $w = 20.0$ mm for segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ and fin spacing optimum of $w = 13.75$ mm for segment orientation $\phi = 90^\circ$ accurately confirm the results of the preliminary study. Notably, another local optimum for segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ can be obtained due to the refined fin spacing resolution, which is situated between $w = 7.5$ mm and $w = 8.75$ mm.

To explain the findings illustrated in Fig. 17, the velocity distribution in the liquid PCM part of the cavity has to be observed in the particular case. As addressed in the explanation of Fig. 15a, the liquid PCM area has to reach a certain size for a strong convection vortex to develop. For this reason, the segments with orientation $\phi = 90^\circ$ show an optimum in fin spacing at around $w = 13$ mm. For wider fin spacings the heat transport via the fins is less effective and convective effects cannot make up this detriment. In case of segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ this optimum is

situated at wider fin spacings, because two separate convection vortices develop due to the symmetry and the necessary liquid area is therefore wider than in the case of orientation $\phi = 90^\circ$.

The local optimum for segment orientation $\phi = 0^\circ$ at fin spacings of about $w = 8$ mm is apparently caused by a breakdown in the symmetry of the liquid PCM flow in the cavity. This leads to the development of a single convection vortex, resulting in enhanced heat transfer and therefore lower charging times. For fin spacings of about $w = 10$ mm this effect subsides, since separate convection vortices develop that are less pronounced than at $w = 20$ mm due to their reciprocal disturbance. Heat transfer is therefore decreased and charging time is slowed. This interesting effect is not obtained for segment orientation $\phi = 90^\circ$ because buoyancy forces are not as significant in such wide and very low fin segments.

4.5. Remark on dimensional analysis

The results discussed above show that the melting process depends on the geometrical and thermal parameters of investigated PCM cavity. As a thorough dimensional analysis of the here presented studies would be extremely comprehensive, only the range of the relevant non-dimensional groups is given. Thus, the main aspects of the fundamental heat transfer mechanics and flow phenomena can be deduced.

The Prandtl number

$$Pr = \frac{c_p \mu}{k} = 17.1 \quad (21)$$

and Stefan number

$$Ste = \frac{c_p \Delta T}{\Delta l_m} = 0.125 \quad (22)$$

are constant throughout all simulated melting cases, where $\Delta T = T_{in} - T_m$ is the temperature difference between the heated wall and the melting temperature. The further relevant non-dimensional numbers are the Rayleigh number

$$Ra = \frac{g \beta \Delta T L^3}{\frac{k}{\rho c_p} \mu}, \quad (23)$$

the Fourier number

Fig. 16. Effect of different fin spacings (5 mm to 100 mm) on time to reach charging level (% of total enthalpy per volume) for fixed aluminium ratio $a = 8\%$ and different segment orientations $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$, $\phi = 90^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

Fig. 17. Effect of different fin spacings (5 mm to 35 mm) on time to reach charging level (% of total enthalpy per volume) for fixed aluminium ratio $a = a\%$ and different segment orientations $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$, $\phi = 90^\circ$ compared to conduction only case.

$$Fo = \frac{k}{\rho c_p} \frac{\tau}{L^2} \quad (24)$$

and the aspect ratio

$$A = \frac{H}{w} = \frac{\Delta x_{PCM}}{w} \quad (25)$$

between the height, i.e. length of the enclosure and the width, which herein corresponds to the fin spacing w [34,84]. In phase-change heat transfer, the dimensionless time τ in the Fourier number Fo is usually the same as the product of Stefan and Fourier numbers, where Ste measures the degree of liquid superheat and Fo the time of thermal diffusion across the distance \tilde{L} [33,84].

The Rayleigh number should be related to buoyancy, hence, in case of $\phi = 90^\circ$, the characteristic length \tilde{L} can be chosen as fin spacing w , also found in literature for PCM enclosures heated from the narrow side (see, for example [85]). In this case, Rayleigh numbers range from $Ra = 9 \cdot 10^3$ to $Ra = 7 \cdot 10^7$ for the studies presented in this work. However, for $\phi = 0^\circ$, the vertical measure Δx_{PCM} should be used as characteristic length \tilde{L} , resulting in a Rayleigh number of $Ra = 1.2 \cdot 10^8$. This approach, using the enclosure height as characteristic length is also found for PCM heated from the wide enclosure side [44]. Other metrics used in literature include, for example, the half-thickness of the PCM layer [86], while it was pointed out that actually a “transient” Rayleigh number for only the liquid part should be calculated [34].

Using the non-dimensional Rayleigh and Fourier number and the aspect ratio, correlations for the liquid phase fraction, convective enhancement and Nusselt number can be obtained for specific problems. However, besides the influence of the aspect ratio, PCM cavity orientation and the varying relation between conductive and convective heat transfer introduced by different volumetric aluminium ratios would have to be considered to generalize the numerical results presented in this work. Common approaches use a modified Stefan number to account for sensible heating of both solid and liquid phases of the PCM [87,84]. Kamkari and Amlashi [48] presented a correlation for the Nusselt number and melting rate under inclination by introducing an additional function of the cavity orientation angle. In Kamkari and Shokouhmand [84], a non-dimensional correlation was presented for the effect of the number of fins on the Nusselt number.

To the best of the author’s knowledge, no dimensional analysis was

conducted to present a correlation for the combined effects of fin spacing, orientation and aluminium ratio on the thermal performance of PCM cavity design as investigated herein. Although we highlight the necessity for further research, we consider such investigation beyond the scope of this work.

5. Conclusions

5.1. Summary of the findings

In the presented parameter study of a rectangular aluminium finned PCM cavity significant angular dependency of the cavity orientation on charging behaviour was observed, whereas the orientation of the cavity was found to have no impact on the discharging behaviour. The influence of natural convection during charging was quantified by means of the convective enhancement factor EF. As could be expected, convective enhancement factors increase with fin spacing in case of upwards-orientated cavities. For downwards-orientated cavities, the impact of natural convection was found negligible for fin spacings of $w = 25$ mm and less, while convective enhancement factors of up to 2 were observed for a fin spacing of $w = 50$ mm.

The impact of aluminium ratio and fin spacing on heat flux during charging was examined in detail. Guideline values for optimal aluminium ratio of the considered cavity geometry of about 15% were found, presenting a trade-off between fast charging time and overall storage capacity. Optimal choices for fin spacing were found for a particular aluminium ratio and cavity orientations $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$. Albeit these particular optima differ, it can be assumed that the optimal fin spacings for segment orientations between $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ are situated between the respective optima and close to the optimum for $\phi = 45^\circ$ due to liquid PCM flow characteristics.

The findings of the present study highlight the crucial effects of aluminium ratio, fin spacing and inclination on the performance of rectangular, finned PCM cavities, therefore showing the importance of design optimization for industrial applications.

5.2. Scope and limitations

The obtained results are of course not directly transferable to general PCM encapsulations and load cycles. A specific geometry was considered meaning a PCM cavity of fixed length with parallel aluminium fins thus

forming narrow fin segments, which are heated from only one of the narrow side walls. Such configurations, however, are found frequently in PCM applications due to its constructional simplicity. Thus, the analysis herein provides at least qualitative findings for a wide range of PCM applications.

Only one type of PCM was investigated in the course of the parameter studies in this work. It should be noted that results for the examined characteristics might differ for other PCM, especially in case of different viscosities or thermal expansion properties. The approximation of specific heat capacity c and heat conductivity k of the studied $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3$ by different, but constant properties for solid and liquid state, as given in Table 1, might differ from reality. Possible quantitative deviations are considered rather small.

5.3. Further research

Since the presented results were only obtained through numerical simulation, experimental investigations should be conducted to confirm or disprove these findings. Similarly useful would be a verification by numerical models based on different methods. Comprehensive dimensional analysis of the presented findings, based on and outlined in Section 4.5 could provide the possibility to scale the results to different geometry and material properties.

To assess the optimal design of a continuous operating LHTES, investigations of a combined charging/discharging scenario are to be conducted.

In Pernsteiner et al. [67], a detailed, high-fidelity co-simulation model of the RSS/PCM segment setup also considered herein is developed. The findings herein are used to attain an efficient model structure and enable deeper design studies and model-based estimation and control tasks [88] for this hybrid storage.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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